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Abstract	The purpose of this document is to show the progress for WP2, task 4.5 and deliverable 4.5 - Algorithms for autonomous drill planning and execution

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History of Changes

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V0.1 (draft)	20 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
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Executive summary

Deliverable D4.5 presents the development and validation of a multi-robot system designed for autonomous drill planning and execution in unstructured and infrastructure-free underground environments. This work is part of Task 4.5 within WP4 of the PERSEPHONE project and focuses on creating a coordinated, perception-driven, and fully autonomous workflow for rock drilling operations. The robotic system includes four specialized agents: the Exploration Robot for navigation and mapping, the Deployer Robot with a manipulator for positioning and scanning, the Supplier Robot for logistics, and the Stinger Robot for drilling. Together, these robots execute a structured mission pipeline starting from scanning the rock face to deploying and anchoring the Stinger Robot and executing the drill plan.

The workflow begins with environmental scanning using a manipulator-mounted LiDAR, generating a high-resolution 3D surface model. From this model, deployment zones are identified based on geometric stability, prioritizing flat and concave regions while avoiding convexities. Several feature detection algorithms were tested for this purpose, including PCA, NRLC, and Normal Tensor Voting (NTV). Among these, NTV showed the best performance by detecting crease features robustly, classifying them into convex and concave categories, and supporting accurate line tracing through seed-growing algorithms. This analysis is critical to identifying safe deployment points for the Stinger Robot's legs and selecting optimal drilling locations that ensure mechanical stability and accuracy. The behaviors of each robot are implemented using the FlexBE framework, enabling hierarchical and modular execution through Hybrid Finite State Machines and Behavior Trees (HFSMBTH). Inter-robot coordination is achieved via a custom communication framework using CycloneDDS for intra-robot communication and Zenoh for distributed inter-robot data exchange. Behavior synchronization, message handling, and distributed task execution ensure smooth collaboration among the fleet.

The system was tested in a Gazebo simulation replicating realistic mine tunnel conditions. Results demonstrate that the integrated framework enables safe and

autonomous drilling operations, validating perception algorithms, communication structure, and behavior coordination. Deliverable D4.5 establishes a robust foundation for future physical deployments, advancing PERSEPHONE's vision for intelligent and autonomous robotic exploration and drilling in underground mining environments.

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1 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
WP	Work package
ROS	Robot Operating System
UR	Universal Robots
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
UPAT	University of Patras
DDS	Data Distribution Service
NAT	Network address translation
PCA	Principal component analysis
NTV	Normal tensor voting
NRLC	Neighbor reweighted local centroid
HFSMBTH	Hybrid Finite State Machines and Behavior Trees
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
KNN	k-Nearest Neighbors
MST	Minimum spanning tree
HFSMs	Hierarchical Finite State Machines
BTs	Behavior Trees

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document presents the design, implementation, and validation of algorithms developed for autonomous drill planning and execution as part of Task 4.5 within WP4 of the PERSEPHONE project. The goal of Task 4.5 is to enable a fully autonomous drilling operation by linking onboard sensor perception of the rock face with the motion planning and execution capabilities of a robotic fleet.

The deliverable focuses on the development of a multi-robot system capable of carrying out exploration drilling operations in unstructured, infrastructure-free underground environments such as abandoned or deep mine sites. It outlines the operational pipeline implemented and validated in a simulated mine setting using Gazebo and ROS 2.

The document details the integration of perception algorithms, motion planning, communication frameworks, and distributed behavior control that together support the coordinated operation of a robotic fleet. By defining the baseline architecture and validating key components in simulation, this deliverable lays the foundation for future deployment and contributes directly to the objectives of the PERSEPHONE project advancing toward a fully autonomous and safe robotic drilling system for underground environments.

2.2 Related documents

- D2.3: Concepts of Next Generation Deep Drilling Systems
- D4.1: Novel path planning and multi-machine coordination algorithms
- D4.2: Sensing methods for detecting drill sites and visual servoing for exploration drilling
- D4.3: Algorithms for sensor-based risk-assessment and traversability analysis
- D4.4: Multi-machine mapping and map merging algorithms validated in simulated environments
- D8.2: Realistic simulation worlds for integrated testing of PERSEPHONE technologies

3 Technical details

This section begins with an overview of the context of the project that guided the developments presented in this deliverable. It then delves into the methodology, providing an in-depth explanation of the technical implementation and underlying concepts. Finally, the results are summarized.

3.1 Overview

Before detailing the technical contributions, this section outlines the overall scenario in which the developed technologies are intended to operate. This deliverable builds upon the system architecture, mission pipeline, and robotic agent definitions established in Deliverable D2.3. It focuses specifically on the algorithms developed for autonomous drill planning and execution within the PERSEPHONE project.

3.1.1 Scenario description

As detailed in D2.3, the PERSEPHONE system is designed to operate in harsh underground mining environments, specifically abandoned and deep mine sites, characterized by limited infrastructure, unpredictable geometry, and environmental hazards such as poor visibility, airborne dust, or dangerous gases. These scenarios require a fully autonomous, infrastructure-free multi-robot solution capable of performing navigation, site characterization, and drilling with minimal human oversight.

3.1.2 Operational Assumptions and Constraints

The robotic system operates under several constraints inherited from the target environments, including:

- Absence of external communication or positioning infrastructure (relying instead on an ad-hoc mesh network and onboard sensing).
- Geometrically constrained 2×2-meter tunnels affect design, mobility, and manipulation strategies.
- The requirement for full autonomy is due to limited prior knowledge of the environment and extreme operational conditions.

These constraints define the boundary conditions for the algorithms developed in D4.5.

3.1.3 Robotic Agent Summary

The robotic fleet, designed and introduced in D2.3, is composed of three key agents:

- **Exploration robot:** Terrain Hopper vehicle equipped with a set of sensors that enable navigation and mapping in unknown environments.
- **Deployer Robot:** Terrain Hopper vehicle equipped with a UR10 manipulator and various sensors (e.g., LiDAR, LIBS, cameras), this robot

handles deployment, perception, and pick-and-place tasks including positioning the drilling robot and characterizing the surrounding rock surface.

- **Supplier Robot:** Terrain Hopper vehicle equipped to provide logistical support: transporting the Stinger Robot, batteries, tools, and drilling consumables to the worksite.
- **Stinger Robot:** A compact, self-anchoring drilling unit capable of executing drilling operations autonomously. It features multiple degrees of freedom for positioning, anchoring, and drilling, along with onboard sensing for validation and local adaptation.

Each agent plays a specialized role in executing the autonomous drill mission pipeline. The algorithms presented in this deliverable build on this architecture to provide coordinated planning, execution, and adaptation mechanisms within the fleet.

For a complete description of the mission pipeline, operational environment, and robotic agent design, please refer to Deliverable D2.3: Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems.

3.2 Methodology

This section will show the details for each of the technical achievements related to D4.5, from high-level mission planning to the implementation of each algorithm that will enable autonomous drill planning and execution.

The development of the technologies presented in this deliverable was supported by the following activities:

- Bi-weekly meetings with the project group
- Consortium meetings
- Workshops with partners
- Lab tests

The entire deliverable has been developed by DTU, with support from LTU, and UPAT for the “Autonomous Refinement of Drilling Plans Based on Onboard Sensing” Section 3.2.3.4.

3.2.1 Autonomous mission planning and workflow

The execution of an autonomous drilling mission within the PERSEPHONE project follows a structured high-level workflow that defines how the fleet of robots collaborates to achieve the mission goals under the scenario conditions described previously.

The autonomous drill planning and execution mission would start once the fleet has reached and aligned itself with the designated drilling location, developed within deliverable D4.2. From that point, the received drill plan is autonomously executed through coordinated actions among the robotic agents. Throughout the operation, the system continuously adapts to the unstructured and partially unknown environment, leveraging onboard sensing and inter-agent communication to ensure robust, flexible, and safe execution.

3.2.1.1 Mission Workflow

Building upon the high-level mission pipeline introduced in Deliverable D2.3, this deliverable presents a more detailed operational workflow focused specifically on autonomous drill planning and execution. While D2.3 outlined the overall structure of the multi-robot mission, here we define how each stage of the drilling operation is realized in practice, specifying which robotic agents are involved and how their roles are determined based on their capabilities and the algorithms implemented in this task.

This workflow bridges system-level mission planning with the concrete execution logic deployed across the fleet, ensuring that each robot performs context-aware actions aligned with its designated function. The result is a coordinated, adaptive, and fully autonomous system capable of executing complex drilling tasks in unstructured underground environments.

The autonomous drilling mission is structured into the following key phases, which define the high-level sequence of operations performed by the robotic fleet:

1. **Arrival at Drilling Area:** The mission begins with the robotic fleet already positioned in proximity to the target drilling location within the mine. The transportation of the robots to this location is handled by the combination of technologies developed and explained in the rest of the deliverables from WP4 (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, and D4.4).
2. **Environment Scanning and Mapping:** The Deployer Robot initiates the mission by performing a detailed scan of the local environment using its onboard sensors and manipulator-mounted devices. The goal of this phase is to generate an accurate 3D representation of the mine surface in the vicinity of the drilling site.
3. **Deployment Area Detection:** Based on the acquired environment map, the Deployer Robot analyzes the surface geometry to identify suitable areas for the deployment of the Stinger Robot. This analysis focuses on detecting planar or concave regions capable of providing stability for the anchoring process while avoiding convex or irregular features. This map is also used to adjust the drill plan if it is needed.
4. **Stinger Robot Deployment:** Once a suitable deployment location has been identified from which the Stinger Robot can execute the drill plan, the Deployer Robot retrieves the Stinger Robot, either from its own payload or from the Supplier Robot, and transports it to the selected position. This phase involves coordinated manipulation and navigation tasks.
5. **Anchoring and Setup:** Upon placement at the deployment site, the Stinger Robot autonomously initiates its anchoring procedure by deploying its legs and arms to attach securely to the mine surface. Simultaneously, the Deployer Robot supplies the necessary resources (power, water, drilling rigs) required to perform the drilling operation.
6. **Drilling Execution:** With the anchoring completed and resources in place, the Stinger Robot executes the drilling plan. Depending on the configuration of its drilling unit, it may perform one or multiple holes

- within the same deployment area by adjusting its internal degrees of freedom.
7. **Repositioning:** If additional drilling points beyond the reach of the current Stinger Robot location are required, the Deployer Robot coordinates the detachment, retrieval, and relocation of the Stinger Robot to a new deployment site. This phase repeats the deployment, anchoring, and drilling processes as necessary.
 8. **Mission Completion:** Once the drilling plan has been successfully completed, the Driller Robot retrieves the Stinger Robot for storage or transport. The fleet then awaits further instructions for either extraction from the mine or relocation to a new operational area.

This structured workflow provides a clear and modular framework for the execution of autonomous drilling missions in unknown underground environments. The definition of distinct mission phases, combined with explicit inter-robot communication at every transition, ensures that all robots maintain a consistent understanding of the mission state and can safely coordinate their actions. While the overall sequence of phases remains consistent across missions, the specific behaviors within each phase are designed to be adaptive, allowing the system to respond to environmental variability, operational constraints, and potential unexpected events during execution.

3.2.2 Communication

The communication network is the same as mentioned in Deliverable 4.4, Section 3.8.

3.2.2.1 Communication Protocols

In our system, we employ different communication protocols based on specific requirements. Given that we are using ROS 2, our choice of middleware and external communication mechanisms is tailored for efficient and reliable data exchange.

3.2.2.2 Internal Communication: CycloneDDS

For internal communication within each robot, we utilize CycloneDDS as the ROS 2 middleware. This is also explained more in Deliverable 4.4, Section 3.8.2.

3.2.2.3 Inter-Robot Communication: Zenoh

For communication between multiple robots, we leverage Zenoh, a data-centric protocol designed for low-latency, distributed systems. Unlike traditional DDS implementations, Zenoh efficiently bridges ROS 2 nodes across different networks by providing pub-sub, query, and storage functionalities.

Why Zenoh over DDS for Inter-Robot Communication?

Although DDS is powerful for real-time communication within a single network, it has limitations when used across distributed environments such as inter-robot

communication over Wi-Fi, ad-hoc networks, or the internet. We chose Zenoh instead of DDS for inter-robot communication because:

- Better performance in low-bandwidth and high-latency networks: DDS relies on multicast discovery, which is inefficient in distributed environments, whereas Zenoh can handle unreliable network conditions more gracefully.
- Flexible network traversal: DDS struggles with firewalls, NAT, and different subnets, requiring additional configurations like domain bridging. Zenoh natively supports communication across different networks without complex setup.
- Lower overhead and bandwidth consumption: Zenoh is designed to minimize network traffic compared to DDS, making it more suitable for wireless and constrained environments.
- Storage and querying capabilities: Unlike DDS, which is purely a pub-sub system, Zenoh supports persistent storage and on-demand data querying, which can be useful for logging, data synchronization, and retrieving past messages.

By combining CycloneDDS for internal communication and Zenoh for inter-robot communication, our system achieves both real-time performance and scalability while maintaining a flexible and efficient architecture.

3.2.2.4 Communication Messages

Effective collaboration is vital to fully exploiting the potential of multirobot systems, as it enables the robots to work together towards achieving common goals. One of the primary challenges in multirobot systems is ensuring clear and reliable communication between the robots, which is essential for reaching consensus and coordinating actions. The way robots interact and communicate significantly influences the behavior of the overall system, making communication a critical component in the design and operation of multi-robot systems.

The development of communication technologies for robots has been inspired by the study of animal communication. Two fundamental characteristics of communication—semantics and arbitrariness—are shared by both human and animal communication modalities. These modalities define the methods through which information is exchanged. To enable robots to effectively communicate, our architecture integrates features that support inter-robot communication, allowing robots to initiate, transfer, and receive communication messages.

The communication messages within our system are structured using ROS2 messages, which adhere to defined semantics. These messages are encapsulated in a custom message type, `Comms.msg`, which contains key information regarding the follow-up task or communication, priority, status, and the type of communication. Each message is associated with a specific topic, formatted as `/comms/<my-name>_comms_<your-name>`, which identifies the initiator and the receiver of the communication. This allows for clear mapping of communication flows between robots. Additionally, the specific task or follow-up information is

conveyed through another topic, /comms/<my-name>_<task_name>, which details the nature of the communication (e.g., information about drilling locations). The message type is designed to accommodate the particular information needed for the exchange, ensuring that the appropriate context and content are communicated.

3.2.3 Algorithms

This section provides a detailed description of the algorithms that have been tested, developed, and implemented to enable autonomous drill planning and execution.

3.2.3.1 Motion Planning of the Manipulator

To carry out autonomous drill planning and execution, we have defined an approach in which a manipulator deploys the Stinger Robot. For this task, the manipulator must perform point-to-point motion planning while considering the constraints of a confined underground environment. To address this, we have adopted MoveIt 2 as our motion planning framework.

As illustrated in the figure below, MoveIt 2 is built on a modular architecture capable of handling diverse types of data. The key components leveraged in our application include:

- Planning pipeline: MoveIt 2 provides a variety of configurable motion planning algorithms. These can be selected and tuned through parameter files, offering the flexibility needed for our specific deployment scenarios.
- Planning scene: This module enables environment awareness by allowing us to define collision objects manually or incorporate live sensor data to dynamically update the map with obstacles.
- Collision detection: By combining planning and scene understanding, MoveIt 2 can generate collision-free trajectories, an essential feature for safe operation in unstructured and cluttered mining environments.
- Visualization: The integrated RViz plugin offers real-time visualization of motion planning results and execution. This significantly accelerates development and debugging by providing immediate feedback during testing.

To improve environmental awareness during manipulation tasks, a LIDAR sensor has been mounted on the manipulator's end-effector. This setup enables the system to actively scan and update the surrounding environment, allowing the manipulator to avoid collisions with the mine's walls, ceiling, and floor. As illustrated in Figure 2, the right image shows the simulated mine environment, while the left image displays the corresponding planning scene used for motion planning. The planning scene is generated from an occupancy map built using the LIDAR point cloud and is used by the manipulator to plan safe trajectories. In addition to the live LIDAR data, predefined collision objects are also included in the occupancy map and considered during planning to further improve collision avoidance. In the planning scene, the vehicle is represented as a green box, while

the LIDAR sensor and end-effector are shown as pink boxes in the left image of Figure 2.

Figure 1: MoveIt2 architecture

Figure 2: MoveIt2 Planning Scene tested in a simulated mine

3.2.3.2 Environment scanning and mapping

Once the robot fleet arrives at the designated drilling site, the environment must be scanned and analyzed to support informed decision-making about how the drilling operation will proceed. Since the characteristics of the area are unknown, a flexible and adaptive scanning procedure is performed using a manipulator equipped with perception sensors such as a LiDAR and a camera.

The area of interest mapping will contain the following phases:

3.2.3.2.1 Initial scan

To begin the process, the manipulator positions itself centrally in front of the Terrain Hopper vehicle and captures a LiDAR scan of the surrounding mine section. The area of interest is defined by the target drilling point and a longitudinal segment of the tunnel centered around it. This region includes the nearby walls, ceiling, and floor, which are critical for evaluating the suitability of deploying the Stinger Robot.

As illustrated in Figure 3:

- The Terrain Hopper vehicle is stationed in front of the designated drilling location (red point).
- The manipulator extends toward the center of the tunnel and acquires a LiDAR scan (white point cloud).
- From this scan, a cropped section of the tunnel (green point cloud) containing the drilling site is extracted for detailed geometric analysis.

Figure 3: Initial Scan

3.2.3.2.2 Adaptable scan

Once the region of interest has been identified, a fine-grained analysis is performed to capture high-resolution data of the wall textures. This is achieved by repositioning the manipulator to bring the sensors closer to the mine walls, allowing for more detailed perception. The following steps outline the process to determine the scanning positions:

- **Flatten initial scan:** The initial scan is flattened along the tunnel's longitudinal axis to generate a 2D representation of the mine section. From this, the inner perimeter is calculated to define the safety boundaries.
- **Safety Scan Perimeter:** The inner perimeter is further offset inward by a configurable parameter called "min wall distance", which defines the minimum safe distance from the tunnel walls. This offset accounts for constraints such as the sensor's minimum range and the physical dimensions of the manipulator's end effector. The resulting safety perimeter, representing the maximum reachable area without risking contact with the walls, is visualized as an orange point cloud.

Figure 4: Adaptable scan

- **Workspace-Constrained Perimeter:** The intersection between the safety scan perimeter (orange) and the manipulator's reachable workspace (represented as a green sphere) defines the workspace-constrained perimeter:
 - If parts of the safety scan perimeter fall within the manipulator's workspace, they are retained directly (orange points within the green sphere).
 - If parts of the safety scan perimeter lie outside the workspace, they are projected to intersect with the workspace boundary to be reachable by the manipulator, resulting in an adjusted scan region (white points within the green sphere).
- **Scan Point Generation:** A configurable parameter determines the number of fine-grained scan positions to generate along the workspace-constrained perimeter. This can be calculated automatically based on the sensor's field of view, ensuring full coverage of the mine section with minimal redundancy. 4 scan points are defined in the example shown in Figure 4.
- **Sensor Pose Estimation:** At each scan point, a sensor frame is computed that orients the sensors to face the target area. These poses are used to move the manipulator and capture high-resolution scans for detailed analysis.

3.2.3.2.3 Merging multiple scans

Once all scan positions are defined, the manipulator moves the sensor to each target location and captures a point cloud of the corresponding wall segment. Each scan is recorded along with its pose in the global reference frame to ensure accurate alignment during merging. Figure 5 illustrates this process: the initial scan from the center position produces the green point cloud, while a follow-up scan from a closer position to the left wall, performed by the manipulator, yields

the denser white point cloud. The increase in point density enhances the level of detail, allowing for more accurate surface analysis of the mine wall.

Figure 5: Closer scan to the wall

After all scan positions have been processed, the individual point clouds are transformed into a common reference frame using their known sensor poses and merged into a single dataset. This merging is done using an implementation of the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm from the pcl library, which aligns each scan based on geometric features such as surface normal and curvature.

The result is a unified, fine-grained point cloud that precisely reconstructs the geometry and texture of the target mine section. This high-resolution representation serves as the foundation for downstream tasks, such as feature extraction, surface classification, and planning of the drilling operation. Figure 6 shows the final merged point cloud (white), offering significantly higher detail compared to the original center scan (green).

Figure 6: Merged point cloud from several scan positions

3.2.3.3 Autonomous Refinement of Drilling Plans Based on Onboard Sensing

To enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the drilling operation, a method was developed to refine the drilling plan based on depth image data collected from the field. This approach leverages surface geometry analysis to optimize drilling locations, ensuring improved contact quality and reduced tool deviation.

The core of the method involves analyzing surface normals derived from the depth images. For each candidate drilling location:

- A local patch was extracted from the depth map centered on the drilling point.
- Surface normals were computed using neighboring depth values through gradient-based or PCA methods.
- The **intra-patch variance** of surface normals was calculated to assess the local planarity and surface consistency.

The refinement process aimed to **minimize the intra-patch surface normal variance**, thereby selecting locations where the surface is most uniformly oriented. This minimizes the risk of tool misalignment and material resistance variation during drilling. Specifically:

- A cost function was defined based on normal vector dispersion within each candidate patch.
- An optimization routine evaluated multiple nearby points and selected the one with the lowest variance.
- The resulting drilling plan contained adjusted coordinates for each hole, optimized for local surface geometry.

Results

The refined drilling plan was validated against the field data. Visual inspection demonstrated improved alignment with the surface contours. The drilling area is first delimited, and an initial drilling plan is generated (represented by the red O in Figure 8). The original drilling plan is then refined by the proposed method, in which a new set of drilling locations is computed (represented by the green X in Figure 8).

Figure 7: Image from the field

Figure 8: The refined drilling plan.

Conclusions

A preliminary version of the drilling plan refinement algorithm was developed and tested using the compiled field data. This initial approach demonstrated

promising results in real-world conditions, confirming the method's practical viability.

- Visual surveying of the machine with respect to the mine face for re positioning the machine to be in a safe space.
- Consider machine dynamics and operational space constraints to align the machine facing the mine face for drilling and excavation tasks.

3.2.3.4 Deployment area detection

Before deploying the Stinger Robot or executing the provided drilling plan, it is essential to analyze the local geometry of the rock face at the drilling location. This assessment is performed using the high-resolution 3D map previously generated by the manipulator-guided scanning procedure executed by the Deployer Robot. The resulting model provides a detailed reconstruction of the rock surface, capturing features such as planes, concavities, convexities, and protruding elements. This geometric information plays a critical role in both the stability of the Stinger Robot during deployment and the feasibility and safety of the drilling plan.

The Stinger Robot relies on stable surface contact to anchor itself securely for drilling. Based on its mechanical configuration, three distinct and stable contact points must be identified on the mine surface for the legs to deploy. These contact points must satisfy the following criteria:

- Preferably planar surfaces orthogonal to the direction of leg extension.
- Alternatively, concave regions that can passively constrain leg motion, reducing the risk of slippage.
- Avoidance of convex or protruding features, which may reduce contact stability or introduce the risk of uncontrolled movement during deployment.

A geometric analysis of the 3D surface model is therefore used to identify feasible configurations where the robot can safely attach itself to the mine walls. As the example shown in Figure 9.

In addition to guiding the deployment of the Stinger Robot, the same surface information is used to evaluate the feasibility of the drilling plan. Drilling into uneven or highly irregular surfaces can induce unwanted lateral forces on the drill bit, leading to bending, wear, or deviation from the desired borehole trajectory. To mitigate this, the system can prioritize the selection of planar or minimally curved surface regions for drilling. This ensures better contact between the drill bit and the rock face, improving the accuracy, safety, and mechanical integrity of the drilling operation.

Figure 9: Stinger Robot contact points requirements. Concave and planar spots are more stable for the legs.

To support these requirements, a detailed geometric understanding of the rock surface is essential. This is achieved by processing the 3D point cloud generated during scanning to extract meaningful structural features such as discontinuities, edges, creases, and smooth regions. These features provide a quantitative basis for evaluating both the deployability of the Stinger Robot and the suitability of specific locations for executing the drilling plan.

Across the literature, most 3D point cloud-based methods for rock surface analysis follow a common multi-stage pipeline that reflects the natural structure of surface interpretation. This pipeline consists of three main steps:

1. **Feature Classification:** Each point in the cloud is analyzed individually to determine whether it belongs to a geometrically significant region (e.g., edges, corners, or flat surfaces), typically using metrics derived from local neighborhood geometry such as curvature, surface normals, or fitting error.
2. **Feature Grouping:** Once feature points are identified, they are clustered into coherent groups based on proximity, similarity of curvature or normal orientation, and other geometric criteria. This step organizes the raw feature points into structured elements that reflect underlying surface patterns.
3. **Line Tracing and Structural Interpretation:** Feature groups are then used to trace continuous lines or segments, often representing creases, ridges, or discontinuities, using algorithms such as seed-growing, Minimum Spanning Trees (MST), or direction-consistent region growing. These traced features are then refined and interpreted to extract meaningful structural information from the surface.

This structured approach allows for the identification of sharp feature points, which we want to avoid. In the following section, we review representative implementations of this feature extraction pipeline, highlighting the specific techniques used and the characteristics of the features they produce.

3.2.3.4.1 Adjacency graph creation

Before feature points can be classified, the point cloud must be structured with a local neighborhood definition. Most feature detection algorithms operate on small surface patches, so defining which points belong to each patch is critical. Common approaches, such as plain k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) or fixed-radius (ϵ -ball) searches, can perform poorly when the point sampling density is non-uniform. To overcome sampling density problems, we have implemented a **symmetric K -Nearest Neighbors (KNN)** approach, as proposed in the paper *Detecting Holes in Point Set Surfaces*. This method ensures that the neighborhood is both spatially representative and robust to variations in point density.

The symmetric $k\epsilon$ -neighborhood of a point P is defined by combining the following sets:

- The **k nearest neighbors (KNN)**: Ensures the k closest points to P are always included.
- The **ϵ -ball neighbors**: All points within a radius ϵ of P , adding spatial coverage beyond the closest k .
- The **reciprocal neighbors**: Points for which P itself appears in their k -NN list, enforcing mutual connectivity.

This combined strategy mitigates the bias that can occur in non-uniformly sampled point clouds. For instance, in areas with varying density, standard KNN may cluster neighbors tightly in high-density zones, while a fixed-radius search might miss sparse regions (left and middle Figure 10). Including reciprocal neighbors helps balance the neighborhood, enriching it with geometrically relevant points regardless of local sampling density (right Figure 10).

Figure 10: Left: $k\epsilon$ -neighborhood is biased towards high density regions. Middle: $k\epsilon$ -neighborhood of the sparse region contains points from the dense region. Right: Symmetric $k\epsilon$ -neighborhood is not affected by varying sampling density. Image from *Detecting Holes*

3.2.3.4.2 NRLC feature detection

An important factor in rock surface analysis is determining whether potential features lie in convex or concave regions. This distinction is critical for Stinger Robot deployment: convex areas should be avoided due to the increased risk of leg slippage, while concave regions can help passively constrain leg movement and improve stability. One algorithm capable of performing this classification is the Neighbor

Rewighted Local Centroid (NRLC). It builds a feature descriptor for each point in the point cloud to assess whether it lies in a convex, concave, or boundary region. The algorithm analyzes each point's local neighborhood by forming vectors from the point to its neighbors and decomposing these vectors into two components: one aligned with the point's surface normal and the other lying in the tangent plane. These components are then accumulated using different weights, capturing the local surface geometry. From this, the algorithm generates a probability distribution for each point, indicating its likelihood of being part of a convex or concave region.

The NRLC algorithm has been implemented and tested using both real and simulated data, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: NRLC algorithm output. a) Real data from a Livox Mid 360, b) Simulated data in Gazebo from a mine model

As illustrated in Figure 11, the algorithm successfully classifies points in concave and convex areas in both environments. When combined with the feature detection techniques described in the previous section, the convex-concave classification can provide complementary geometric information, contributing to a more complete and potentially more robust rock surface analysis pipeline.

However, this algorithm does not provide a direct classification of points within flat surfaces or edges, which is needed to decide where to deploy the Stinger Robot.

3.2.3.4.3 PCA feature detection

One of the most extended methods for point clouds feature extraction is PCA. Based on the eigenvalues and vectors analysis, points can be classified as borders, edges, corners, and flat spots.

The first step in the PCA analysis involves constructing a local neighborhood around each point, as explained in the previous section. For each symmetric neighborhood, the local covariance matrix is calculated and decomposed with Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The resulting eigenvectors provide the principal directions of variation, while the corresponding eigenvalues quantify

how widely the points spread along each direction; together they form a correlation ellipsoid that captures the local surface shape as seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Shape of the correlation ellipsoid for different neighbor points. a) surface point, b) crease point, c) border point, d) corner point. Picture from *Feature extraction from pointclouds* paper

A similar approach to the one proposed in *Feature extraction from pointclouds* has been implemented. The idea is to compute point penalty weights based on the correlation ellipsoid shape, so the lower weights indicate potential crease and corner feature points.

In flat surface regions, the two largest eigenvalues of the local covariance matrix tend to be similar ($\lambda_1 \approx \lambda_2$), while the smallest eigenvalue is close to zero ($\lambda_0 \approx 0$), indicating a flattened correlation ellipsoid. As the surface becomes more curved, λ_0 increases, reflecting greater variance in the third direction. This observation allows for a curvature estimation by the following equation:

$$k = \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_0 + \lambda_1 + \lambda_2}$$

This curvature can be translated into a curvature-based penalty function.

$$w_k = 1 - \min\left(\frac{k}{k_{max}}, 1\right)$$

For crease or edge detection, the ellipsoid becomes elongated along the direction of the crease. In such cases, the smallest and middle eigenvalues are approximately equal ($\lambda_0 \approx \lambda_1$), and their sum is close to the largest eigenvalue ($\lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \approx \lambda_2$). These relationships can be used to define the following crease penalty function:

$$w_{cr} = \frac{\max(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0, |\lambda_2 - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_0)|)}{\lambda_2}$$

Finally, in corner regions where the local surface has significant variation in all directions, the three eigenvalues become similar ($\lambda_0 \approx \lambda_1 \approx \lambda_2$). This results in a near-spherical ellipsoid with no clear principal direction, and a corresponding corner penalty function can be defined to capture this geometric property.

$$w_{co} = \frac{\lambda_2 - \lambda_0}{\lambda_2}$$

Figure 13 shows the normalized point penalty weights for each class independently. As a sample, a surface with several creases is used.

Figure 13: a) Surface containing creases, b) Normalized curvature weights, c) Normalized crease weights, d) Normalized corner weights

By examining the results, we observe that curvature and corner weights (Figure 13 b and d) effectively highlight feature points distributed along both sharp and smooth creases. However, the crease weight map (Figure 13 c) primarily emphasizes the most prominent edges and the borders of the point cloud, failing to capture smooth edges. This limitation suggests that crease weights are not fully reliable for detecting creases, as they introduce false positives at the cloud boundaries.

Once each point has been assigned to a geometric class, the next objective is to extract coherent crease patterns that capture the structural characteristics of the surface. To derive these patterns, neighboring classified points are connected via edges, with each edge weighted according to the penalty weights of the connected points. By computing paths of minimal cumulative weight across this graph, the most probable crease lines can be extracted.

For crease pattern extraction, we adopt an edge weighting strategy inspired by *Feature Extraction from Point Clouds*. The crease weight for each edge incorporates three components: a curvature-based term, a corner-based term, and an edge length term that favors shorter connections. Notably, the crease-based term is excluded due to its tendency to misclassify borders as crease features, as previously demonstrated.

$$w_c(e = (p, q)) = \alpha \cdot (w_k(p) + w_k(q)) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (w_{co}(p) + w_{co}(q)) + \frac{2|e|}{\mu(p) + \mu(q)}$$

As illustrated in Figure 14a, edges connecting likely crease features are emphasized in white, indicating that the computed edge weights effectively capture the location and continuity of structural creases within the point cloud.

a)

b)

Figure 14: Line tracing pipeline combining weighted edges and a modified MST: a) Crease edge weights. Potential crease edges are highlighted in white. b) Feature lines detected by the modified MST

Once the crease-weighted edges are computed from the point cloud, a modified Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) is implemented to extract meaningful edge traces along geometric features. The MST is built by sorting edges based on the previously calculated weights, so that edges with lower weights (stronger feature likelihood) are prioritized. As the graph is built, edges that would form cycles are usually skipped unless the resulting loop exceeds a threshold length (θ), allowing for long structural cycles while avoiding short, noisy loops. During the final stage, short terminal branches are pruned, resulting in a pattern graph that follows prominent surface creases. The output can be seen in Figure 14b. As can be seen, the white potential edges have been detected as edges by the green lines. However, many false edges have been detected, creating many loops that need to be pruned.

These results highlight that, while the PCA method can give potential weights to point features, the line tracing feature detection method based on the modified MST directly in the whole point cloud is not effective, as non-connected features are forced to be connected by the tree.

3.2.3.4.4 Normal Tensor Voting feature detection

Normal Tensor Voting (NTV) is a feature analysis method that captures local surface geometry by analyzing the variation of normals within a point's neighborhood. After defining a symmetric neighborhood around each point, NTV constructs a second-order symmetric tensor. This tensor encodes the dominant orientation trends in the local region. By performing eigenvalue decomposition on the tensor, the principal eigenvectors reveal the main directions of normal variation, while the eigenvalues indicate the strength of alignment along those directions. The resulting orientation ellipsoid characterizes the local shape: a strong dominant direction suggests a surface patch, two similar eigenvalues suggest an edge, and three similar values indicate a corner or noisy region. This makes NTV especially effective for detecting sharp features and understanding geometric structure in unorganized point clouds.

To identify geometric features with Normal Tensor Voting, we look at the eigenvalues of each point. We obtain ordered eigenvalues $\lambda_0 \leq \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2$. Along a

crease, normals vary strongly in exactly one direction that is perpendicular to the crest; this inflates the second eigenvalue λ_1 while λ_0 stays small. Consequently, we mark a point as a potential edge point whenever $\lambda_1 > \alpha$. The potential feature points can be seen in Figure 15b, highlighted in yellow.

Once potential feature points are detected, points are classified into concave and convex features. For each candidate point, it analyzes the distribution of neighboring normals on both sides of the edge direction. If the normals from both sides point inward toward the edge, the point is labeled as concave. If they both point outward, the point is labeled as convex. If the orientation is mixed or ambiguous, the point is discarded from classification.

The detected concave and convex potential feature points are divided into meaningful groups. A random point is selected, and its edge direction is taken as the group's direction. All neighbors that have an edge direction difference below a threshold with the group direction are added as part of the group. This process is repeated until all the points have been grouped. The result of this operation is shown in Figure 15c, where each group has a different colour.

Finally, the line tracing function extracts meaningful feature traces from the groups. It first applies PCA to each group to determine the main orientation and identify a start and end point. It then performs a greedy path-following algorithm beginning at the starting point. At each step, it selects the best neighbor that both aligns with the current edge direction and has a high edge strength, prioritizing forward growth along the trace. This generates ordered sequences of points that follow the underlying geometry, producing well-formed trace lines representing the structural features of the surface. The feature lines are shown in Figure 15d as white lines. It can also be seen how each line below corresponds to a classified concave (green) or convex (red) region.

Figure 15: NTV feature classification process: a) analyzed surface, b) feature points, c) feature points grouping, d) feature lines tracing.

In the following Figures 16 and 17, several surfaces with different types of creases can be seen, and the output of the proposed NTV method is highlighted as white lines.

a) b)
Figure 16: Test surface 2. a) surface, b) NTV algorithm output

a) b)
Figure 17: Test surface 3: a) surface, b) NTV algorithm output

3.2.3.4.5 Feature detection algorithms conclusion

To identify suitable deployment areas for the Stinger Robot, namely flat or concave surfaces that offer mechanical stability, three feature detection algorithms were implemented and evaluated: NRLC, PCA, and NTV.

The NRLC algorithm effectively classifies points as concave or convex by analyzing the distribution of local surface normals. This classification is directly relevant for assessing contact stability, as concave regions passively constrain the Stinger's legs. However, NRLC does not distinguish between other critical geometric features such as edges, corners, or flat surfaces. This limitation reduces its utility for holistic surface assessment, particularly in identifying deployment regions with planar support or structural boundaries.

The PCA-based method offers more detailed geometric descriptors. By analyzing the local covariance matrix, PCA identifies flat regions, creases, and corners based on eigenvalue relationships. These descriptors are well-suited for deployment assessment and drilling feasibility. The PCA-derived point weights provide an intuitive map of rock geometry. However, the subsequent line tracing using a

modified Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) introduces significant limitations. While the PCA weighting scheme correctly highlights edge features, MST-based line extraction produces many false positives and artificial loops, requiring extensive pruning.

The Normal Tensor Voting (NTV) method shows the most promising performance for detecting relevant geometric features on rock surfaces. By analyzing the variance of normals in local neighborhoods, NTV robustly captures creases and edges, even in unstructured or noisy environments. Furthermore, the custom concave/convex classifier based on normal orientation distributions adds valuable context for deployment decisions. Grouping of these features based on edge direction similarity enables clean segmentation of surface structures. When paired with a seed-growing algorithm that prioritizes continuity in edge direction and local feature strength, the NTV-based approach reliably traces creases with minimal parameter tuning.

Overall, the NTV method yields the most robust and informative results for identifying stable deployment areas and structural features. Future improvements could include a hybrid approach that combines the global shape sensitivity of PCA with the directional sensitivity of NTV, leading to a more comprehensive and noise-resilient feature classifier. Additionally, while the seed-growing strategy for line tracing performs well, its accuracy depends heavily on the initial feature grouping. A refinement stage to merge fragmented lines or correct small discontinuities could significantly enhance the continuity and precision of the extracted feature lines.

3.2.4 Behavior-Based Control

The paper [1] presents a compelling argument for adopting HFSMBTH—a hybrid approach that combines Hierarchical Finite State Machines (HFSMs) and Behavior Trees (BTs)—over using either HFSMs or BTs in isolation. The rationale is based on the need for more adaptable, modular, and collaborative control architectures in modern robotic systems.

Why Not Just HFSMs?

HFSMs have long been a standard for modeling complex robot behaviors due to their clear state-based logic and well-understood transition mechanisms. However, as the complexity of robotic tasks grows, especially in collaborative, multi-agent, or dynamic environments, HFSMs tend to become brittle and monolithic. They are difficult to scale, reuse, or dynamically adapt. The rigid transition structure of HFSMs often leads to "spaghetti logic" where handling exceptions or inserting new behaviors requires rewriting or untangling significant parts of the control flow.

Why Not Just BTs?

BTs, on the other hand, were introduced as a modular and reactive alternative. They excel in organizing behaviors hierarchically and in supporting interruptibility and fallback strategies through constructs like selectors and

sequences. BTs also promote behavior reuse and composability, making them more maintainable and readable. However, BTs struggle when dealing with strict sequencing or internal state-dependent transitions that go beyond what their tree structure can naturally encode. BTs can also become less intuitive when used to express complex control logic that involves deeply nested conditions or when fine-grained control over transitions is necessary.

Why HFSMBTH?

The hybrid model—HFSMBTH—leverages the strengths of both paradigms. By combining HFSMs' rigorous state transition logic with BTs' modular and reactive structure, HFSMBTH enables systems that are both robust and flexible. In this hybrid architecture, developers can encode high-level mission plans using HFSMs, taking advantage of their strong control over transitions and execution paths. Within each high-level state, BTs can be used to manage subtasks or respond to environmental conditions dynamically, benefiting from BTs' ability to react to changes and support behavior reuse.

This hybrid model becomes especially valuable in collaborative autonomy, where robots need to react in real time to changes not only in the environment but also in the behavior of other agents. HFSMBTH provides the predictability required for coordination and the reactivity necessary for autonomy. It also allows for clearer separation of concerns: HFSMs govern *when* a behavior should be executed, while BTs govern *how* it should unfold.

In essence, HFSMBTH provides a structured yet flexible framework that supports complex behavior composition, improves modularity, and scales better with task complexity. It aligns well with the requirements of modern robotics, where autonomy, collaboration, and adaptability are key. By not forcing a choice between HFSM and BT but instead integrating them, HFSMBTH addresses their individual shortcomings and delivers a more capable behavior architecture.

HFSMBTH Tool

FlexBE (Flexible Behavior Engine) is a high-level behavior modeling tool designed specifically for robotics applications, particularly those developed within the ROS (Robot Operating System) ecosystem. It serves as a practical implementation of the HFSMBTH concept—the hybrid of Hierarchical Finite State Machines (HFSMs) and Behavior Trees (BTs)—by enabling the design, execution, and monitoring of complex robot behaviors in a structured yet flexible way.

What FlexBE Does

At its core, FlexBE allows developers to construct behaviors as state machines, where each state can encapsulate fine-grained decision-making and reactive logic akin to BTs. This hybrid structure lets roboticists manage both long-term task planning and short-term responsiveness within a single coherent framework.

Key Features That Enable HFSMBTH:

- **Hierarchical States:** FlexBE supports nested state machines, allowing high-level states to contain entire sub-behaviors. This reflects the HFSM aspect—where the control flow can be organized in layers, from strategic tasks down to tactical actions.
- **Reusability and Modularity:** Like BTs, FlexBE encourages the reuse of behaviors. Individual states (nodes) or behaviors can be reused across different tasks or machines. This modularity simplifies the development of complex robotic applications and supports collaborative autonomy by enabling shared behavior libraries.
- **Reactive Execution:** States in FlexBE can react to runtime information—sensors, user inputs, or external commands—allowing behaviors to adapt dynamically during execution. This mimics the reactive and interruptible nature of BTs while maintaining state-based control.
- **Graphical Interface:** FlexBE includes a GUI that makes it easier to visualize, construct, and debug behavior of logic. This helps users manage large and complex behavior trees/state machines by providing a clear overview of transitions, conditions, and nested structures.
- **Runtime Introspection and Control:** During execution, developers can monitor the state transitions in real time, trigger manual transitions, and inspect inputs and outputs. This is critical for debugging and human-in-the-loop operations—important for collaborative autonomy.
- **Integration with ROS:** FlexBE states are implemented as Python classes that can directly interface with ROS topics, services, and actions. This makes it highly practical for real-world robotics projects, enabling tight coupling between behavior logic and robot capabilities.

Why FlexBE Fits HFSMBTH

FlexBE realizes the vision of HFSMBTH by blending structured transitions (HFSM) with reactive, goal-driven execution (BT-like logic). A developer can, for example, define a high-level "Explore" behavior that conditionally transitions to sub-behaviors like "Navigate to Goal", "Avoid Obstacle", or "Recharge Battery", each of which can contain lower-level reactive sequences. This combination enables a robot to handle both planned workflows and unexpected situations without losing behavioral coherence.

In short, FlexBE enables developers to build intelligent, adaptable, and modular robotic behaviors by combining the rigor of finite state logic with the flexibility of reactive behavior trees, fulfilling the promise of HFSMBTH in a practical, usable framework.

3.2.5 Communication Behavior

We introduce two concepts for developing communication behavior. Users can develop communication behavior based on the execution of tasks.

Definition 1: SyncAction State The *SyncAction* state is a control mechanism designed to evaluate both the robot's individual actions (denoted as R_a) and the conditions required for inter-robot communication simultaneously during each

execution cycle. While the state is active, a periodic execution loop—referred to as *loop3*—is triggered at regular intervals. This concurrent evaluation ensures that the robot's actions are kept in sync with those of its peers. Such synchronization is particularly important for strongly coupled tasks, where multiple robots must act in unison within dynamic and potentially unpredictable environments.

Definition 2: Comms State In contrast to the SyncAction state, the *Comms* state focuses exclusively on evaluating inter-robot communication conditions during its execution loop. It plays a critical role in managing the activation or deactivation of robot sub-behaviors based on communication events.

Whenever a robot sends (mt) or receives (mr) a communication message, it updates a shared knowledge base (Kb) that stores the current state of communication. This knowledge base serves as a reference point for determining when to trigger or halt specific sub-behaviors, enhancing coordination among robots.

Communication messages in this system are categorized into two types: basic and task specific. The basic communication message includes the following key fields:

- **Comms Type (Ct):** Indicates whether the associated task is strongly or weakly coupled. It is a boolean value:
 - True — for strongly coupled tasks (requiring tight coordination)
 - False — for weakly coupled tasks (requiring minimal coordination)
- **Comms Status (Cs):** Represents the intermediary steps in a collaborative process, such as "message received" or "sub-task completed." This allows each robot to maintain a lightweight overview of the state of team members it has communicated with. It also supports feedback mechanisms within the communication loop.
- **Comms Task (Cn):** Refers to the identifier of the next communication message, typically pointing to more detailed task-specific information.

Using these states and communication message structures, two pseudocode templates are defined:

- **Algorithm 1** — for strongly coupled collaborative tasks
- **Algorithm 2** — for weakly coupled collaborative tasks

Algorithm 1 Pseudo code for strongly coupled collaborative task: SyncAction State (S)

Arguments: R_a, C_t, C_s, C_n, O
on_enter event
Execute R_a
while S is active **do**
 if $C_t = False$ **then**
 return $O_0 \sim S = Deactivate$
 end if
 Evaluate: $R_a \wedge C_s \wedge N_r \xrightarrow{\text{output}} E_i$
 if $E_i = True$ **then**
 Comms: $m_t \vee m_r$
 Update: K_b
 return O_i
 end if
end while
on_exit event

Figure 18: Algorithm 1 for strongly coupled collaborative tasks

Algorithm 2 Pseudo code for weakly coupled collaborative task: Comms State (S)

Arguments: C_t, C_s, C_n, O
on_enter event
Evaluate: $K_b \wedge C_s \wedge C_n \wedge N_r \xrightarrow{\text{output}} E_i$
while S is active $\wedge E_i$ is not None **do**
 if $C_t = True$ **then**
 return $O_0 \sim S = \text{Deactivate}$
 end if
 if $E_i = True$ **then**
 Comms: $m_t \vee m_r$
 return O_i
 end if
end while
on_exit event: Update K_b

Figure 19: Algorithm 2 for weakly coupled collaborative tasks

These algorithms serve as basic templates for implementation.

Each state can have a n number of possible outcomes: $O_i \in \{O1, O2, \dots, On\}$
The outcome result from evaluations (E_j) based on at least three parameters:

- **Ra** — the robot's current action
- **Cs** — communication status
- **Ni** — network status of robot i

A key component of Nr is the boolean parameter, which determines whether the r -th robot is within communication range:

- True — if the robot is in range
- False — if it is out of range

3.2.6 Distributed Behavior

In our distributed robotic system, each robot operates autonomously with behavior tailored to its specific task execution capabilities. These behaviors are designed using the FlexBE (Flexible Behavior Engine) framework and are structured in a modular, hierarchical state machine format.

For instance, the three-legged stinger robot specializes in drilling tasks. It has its own independent behavior that governs how it executes those tasks once deployed. However, before the stinger robot can begin its operation, it must be

physically deployed into the workspace. This responsibility is handled by the UR10 robotic arm, which functions as the deployer robot.

The coordination between the UR10 and the stinger robot is a prime example of distributed behavior, where autonomous robots communicate and collaborate to achieve a shared mission objective. Each robot executes its own behavior locally, but inter-robot coordination is achieved through defined communication states and shared status variables.

3.2.6.1 Deployer Robot (Manipulator): Behavior Overview

Figure 20: Deployer robot behavior

The deployer robot's behavior is defined in a FlexBE state machine named Sim Mani Demo 3. This behavior includes the following sequence of distributed and local tasks:

- **Initialize the Environment:** The Simulation Initializing Workspace sub-behavior sets up the simulated environment, placing virtual objects for collision avoidance and preparing the workspace for deployment.
- **Move to Home Position:** The HomePose state brings the robot's end effector to a predefined "home" pose. This ensures the robot starts from a known, safe configuration before beginning complex actions.
- **Move to Deployment Pose:** The Sim Kinematic Move End Effector sub-behavior calculates and executes the motion needed to bring the robot's end effector to the correct position for deployment.
- **Grasp the Stinger Robot:** Using the CloseGripper state, the manipulator secures the stinger robot by closing its gripper via a trajectory controller.
- **Deploy the Stinger Robot:** The Sim4 Deploying Geo Miner sub-behavior executes the deployment sequence, carefully placing the stinger robot into the workspace. This may involve position adjustments and tool interactions.

- **Inter-Robot Communication:** After deployment, the manipulator uses the V2Comms state to communicate with the supplier robot. A task name (e.g., "BringResources") is sent, signaling that the supplier robot can begin its behavior. This state demonstrates distributed coordination, where autonomous robots synchronize based on task progression.

3.2.6.2 Distributed System Highlights

- **Autonomous Execution:** Each robot runs its own behavior state machine independently.
- **Namespace-based Communication:** Communication states (like V2Comms) are used to exchange task status or triggers using ROS namespaces, enabling task handoff between robots.
- **Modular Behavior Design:** Behaviors such as Sim Kinematic Move End Effector and Sim4 Deploying Geo Miner are encapsulated and reusable, making the system scalable and maintainable.

This modular and distributed structure allows for scalable multi-robot coordination where robots can be added or removed with minimal changes to the overall system behavior. The deployer robot's role is critical in initializing the operation pipeline by deploying and communicating with task-specific robots like the stinger.

3.2.7 Developed Behaviors

The behaviors were developed upon algorithms, communication, and distributed behavior explained in the sections above. The behaviors are a generalized sequence of possible actions and communication defining the mission workflow.

3.2.7.1 Deployer Behavior

Figure 21: Deployer robot behavior

The behavior shown in Figure 21 is developed to be executed after the Deployer robot has positioned itself for deploying the Stinger robot. This behavior is embedded inside the Sim Mani Demo3 (see Figure 21). The states used in the behavior are explained below:

- **OpenGripper:** Ensures the gripper of the manipulator is open in preparation for gripping.
- **GeoMiner Location:** Identifies the location of the stinger robot in the environment.
- **Sim Kinematic Move End Effector:** Computes the feasible trajectory of the manipulator and executes the trajectory.
- **Adjusting Pose:** Minor corrections to align end effector position for picking up stinger robot.
- **FindEEPose:** Computes the current position of the manipulator's end effector.
- **PickUp Pose and Approaching To PickUp:** Computes and executes the trajectory to approach the stinger robot for gripping action.
- **HoldGeoMiner:** Closes the gripper to grasp the stinger robot securely.
- **AttachGeoMiner:** Attaching the stinger robot to the end effector of the manipulator.
- **HoldUp and PickUp Move:** Computes and executes the trajectory to lift the stinger robot.
- **GeoMinerCenter and Move To Deployment Center:** Computes and executes the trajectory to transport the stinger robot to the designated drilling location.
- **DeploymentSignal:** Sends the deployment configuration to the stinger robot through communication behavior.
- **Drilling Details:** Shares the drilling operation details with the stinger robot to initiate the drilling process.

The above states are executed in the logical flow depicted in Figure 21.

3.2.7.2 Stinger Robot Behavior

Figure 22: Stinger Robot behavior

The behavior shown in Figure 22 deploys the Stinger robot in the drilling location. The first state is the StandBy State. In this state, called StandbyState, the robot named Stinger robot waits to receive a message from another robot named deployer robot. This message is expected to arrive on a communication channel named `/comms/deployer_comms_stinger`, which follows a naming pattern

indicating that deployer robot is sending the message and stinger robot is the intended receiver.

The purpose of the state is to pause and do nothing until it receives a message that contains a specific instruction. In this case, it's waiting for a message where the task name is HingePoints. That task name acts as a signal; once this exact instruction is received, the state considers the message valid and allows the robot to move on to its next step.

Until the correct message is received, the robot stays in this standby condition, periodically checking whether any new message has arrived and whether it includes the expected task name. As soon as the task name "HingePoints" is detected, the state logs that it is ready, sets an internal status value (used by later states), and then transitions to the next state in the behavior.

This approach allows coordination between two robots. One robot (in this case, the Deployer) controls when the other robot (Stinger Robot) should proceed with a particular task; in this situation, the task is called "HingePoints". It's a synchronization mechanism that ensures the two robots stay in step during a collaborative operation.

The purpose of this behavior is to control the Stinger Robot so it can be deployed for the drilling operation according to the information provided by the Deployer Robot. The behavior is structured as a series of coordinated steps, each performed only when certain conditions are met or signals are received from the other robot.

Step-by-Step Flow:

- **StandBy:** The process starts with the stinger robot waiting for a signal from deployer robot. Specifically, it waits for a message containing the task name "HingePoints" on a communication channel meant for messages from deployer to stinger robot. This acts as a green light from deployer robot, telling stinger robot to start its support routine. If the correct message is received, it proceeds to the next step; if not, it fails.
- **Centering:** Once the start signal is received, the stinger robot moves to a centered position. This is likely a preparatory pose to ensure it's aligned correctly before deploying its support legs. The state listens on the /stinger_joint_trajectory_controller/follow_joint_trajectory action topic to perform the centering movement. If the centering succeeds, it continues; otherwise, it transitions to failure.
- **HingeState:** After centering, the robot deploys its support legs by moving to a "hinge" pose. This movement is also executed through the same trajectory controller. If the deployment is successful, it moves to the next waiting phase. If the movement fails or times out, the behavior ends with failure.
- **WaitForDrillSignal:** Now that the robot is in position and its legs are deployed, it waits again for a signal from the Deployer robot, this time for the actual drilling instruction. It listens to a task named "DrillPoint", which

contains specific drilling parameters like radius, displacement, and depth. Only when this data is received correctly does it move forward.

- **Drill:** With the drilling instructions received, the stinger robot now assists in the actual drilling operation. It uses the previously received parameters (drad, ddisp, ddepth) and moves accordingly through the trajectory controller. When drilling is complete, the behavior ends with success. If there's any failure or cancellation, it ends with a failure.

Final Outcomes:

- If all steps are completed successfully, the behavior finishes with the "finished" outcome.
- At any step, if there's an error (e.g., no message received, timeout, movement failure), it ends with the outcome "failed".

Figure 23: Deployer and Stinger Robot behavior. Deployer robot behavior: a) Deployer moving to pick up the Stinger Robot, b) Deployer closing gripper, c) Deployer moving to deploy the Stinger robot. Stinger robot behavior: d) Stinger robot opens stingers, e) Stinger robot extends the stingers, f) Stinger robot drills.

Figure 23 illustrates the deployment and drilling behavior of the Stinger Robot within a simulated mine environment. The operation involves three coordinated robots: the Deployer Robot, equipped with a manipulator for handling and placement tasks; the Supplier Robot, responsible for transporting the Stinger Robot and necessary resources; and the Stinger Robot itself, which autonomously performs the anchoring and drilling operations once deployed.

3.3 Results

In this section, we have presented the technical developments achieved for Deliverable D4.5 within WP4. The work marks a significant step toward enabling autonomous operation of a coordinated fleet of robots by defining a structured

operational workflow that guides the system through the key stages of drill planning and execution. This mission pipeline has served as the foundation for designing and implementing the supporting technical components.

The workflow begins with the assumption that the robotic fleet required for drilling is already positioned at the target location. The second phase, Environment Scanning and Mapping, involves generating a detailed map of the drilling area to support accurate placement and adaptive drill planning for the Stinger Robot. To achieve this, an autonomous, manipulator-guided mapping routine has been developed. This approach adapts to the unknown and irregular geometries of mine tunnels, producing high-resolution point clouds of the rock face.

In the third phase, Deployment Area Detection, the generated map is analyzed to identify stable and secure regions for deploying the Stinger Robot. To support this step, geometry-based classification algorithms have been developed and tested, demonstrating their ability to identify suitable deployment surfaces based on local rock features and structural stability. In addition, an initial drill plan refinement algorithm has been implemented.

The fourth phase, Stinger Robot Deployment, enables the coordinated operation between the Deployer robot and the Stinger Robot to autonomously perform the deployment sequence. A behavior model has been implemented to manage decision-making and inter-robot coordination, allowing the system to carry out the deployment without human intervention by leveraging shared knowledge and real-time data exchange.

Each phase of the workflow requires robust inter-robot communication and collaboration. To support this, a comprehensive communication framework has been implemented. BATMAN has been adopted to establish an ad-hoc wireless network, while Zenoh has been integrated to handle inter-robot communication. Internally, each robot relies on ROS 2 with CycloneDDS for real-time data handling. FlexBE has been selected to manage mission behaviors, enabling hierarchical state machines that coordinate high-level planning with low-level control. Custom communication messages have also been defined to facilitate structured interactions between robots, allowing them to request and share resources as needed throughout the mission.

Figure 24: Event timeline for the Deployer actions and communication

The distributed behaviors in the system demonstrate a tightly coupled and well-coordinated interaction between multiple robots. As illustrated in Figure 24, the deployment of the Stinger Robot is initiated by the deployer’s manipulator, referred to as MANI, through an inter-robot communication channel labeled **Comms_(MANI-GeoMiner)**

Initially, the **Stinger Robot** remains in a standby state, awaiting a deployment signal. Once MANI transmits the signal along with the corresponding **deployment pose**, the Stinger Robot begins its autonomous deployment sequence (**GeoMiner_Action**). This sequence consists of three key actions:

1. **Position Arms and Extend Arms (Stabilization):** The first two actions involve unfolding or hinging the robot’s legs to achieve a stable configuration suitable for drilling operations.
2. **Drilling:** The final action executes the actual drilling process at the designated location.

Throughout this process, the Stinger Robot provides real-time feedback to the deployer robot (MANI) via **Comms_(GeoMiner-MANI)**, reporting the status and success of each step.

After the Stinger Robot has been successfully deployed and is operational, MANI communicates the completion of the deployment to a third robot, referred to as the **supplier robot**, using the communication link **Comms_(MANI-V2)**.

This entire sequence illustrates a coordinated and autonomous deployment pipeline, showcasing the effectiveness of inter-robot communication in orchestrating complex tasks across a multi-robot system.

Figure 25: Event timeline for the Stinger robot actions and communication

Figure 26: Event timeline for the Supplier actions and communication

3.3.1 Progress in relation to DoA

The technical achievements presented in Deliverable D4.5 are well aligned with the objectives and scope defined in Task 4.5 and Deliverable D4.5 of the Description of Action (DoA). The task focuses on the autonomous planning and execution of drilling operations by developing a perceive-and-act framework capable of identifying optimal drilling locations, performing robotic manipulation, and executing the drill plan with high accuracy.

This deliverable defines the foundational elements for autonomous drill planning and execution, as detailed in Section 3.2.1.1 Mission Workflow. Building on this baseline, key developments have been carried out that support the integration of perception and motion planning, enabling the system to interpret sensor data

from the rock face and generate corresponding manipulation actions without human intervention.

Furthermore, a communication framework has been developed to support inter-robot coordination, which is essential for the modular and collaborative system architecture envisioned in the project. These developments reflect steady progress toward the goals of Task 4.5 and confirm alignment with the intended direction set out in the DoA.

The development and validation of these components have been conducted in a simulation environment that emulates realistic mine tunnel conditions, allowing safe and repeatable testing of the complete workflow under representative spatial and sensing constraints.

4 Partners contributions

Task 4.5 is led by the DTU team, focusing on the development of algorithms for autonomous drill planning and execution based on onboard sensing of rock face characteristics. LTU contributed by providing DTU with processed point cloud maps of the mine, which were generated from data collected during a joint field effort led by LTU, DTU, and UPAT, in close collaboration with MRP and KGHM. The mine facilities were made available by KGHM for this data collection campaign, which took place in November 2024. Throughout the course of Task 4.5, EPI actively participated in WP4 planning discussions and hosted the DTU team at their test mine and facilities in Örebro, Sweden.

5 Future plans

Building on the foundation established in Deliverable D4.5, several development and validation activities are planned to advance the autonomous drill planning and execution system:

- Refine and evaluate the implemented perception algorithms to improve the robustness and accuracy of geometric rock surface analysis under varying conditions. This will continue within Task 5.5.
- Integrate and validate control strategies for the Stinger Robot during anchoring and setup operations when attached to the rock face. This task will continue within Task 5.5 .
- Implement and test autonomous drill execution capabilities for the Stinger Robot, based on the drilling mechanism design detailed in Deliverable D2.3. This work will be carried out under Task 5.5, in close collaboration with Task 3.1, which focuses on the mechanical development of the drilling unit. The integration of software and hardware components across these tasks will be realized through coordinated efforts in WP9, specifically within Tasks 9.1 and 9.2, enabling system-level integration and iterative testing in simulated and controlled environments.
- Develop and deploy a fully distributed behavior coordination system across the robot fleet, enabling autonomous task allocation and execution without external supervision. The coordination behaviors outlined in this deliverable will be implemented and extended throughout the remaining tasks in WP5, serving as the foundation for collaborative autonomy. This system will facilitate seamless integration of all WP5 contributions within Task 9.1, supporting system-level integration and multi-agent coordination under the broader PERSEPHONE architecture.
- Mission-level tests of the communication framework will be conducted to ensure reliable coordination and data exchange across all robotic agents during full operational scenarios. These tests will validate the system's ability to support decentralized decision-making, task distribution, and real-time sensor sharing in multi-robot missions. Continued development and validation will take place through Tasks 5.1, 5.4, and 5.5, enabling robust and scalable communication capabilities essential for effective fleet-wide collaboration within the PERSEPHONE project.

These steps will contribute to a fully autonomous and collaborative drilling operation, aligned with the overall objectives of Task 4.5 and the broader PERSEPHONE project.

6 Conclusions

Deliverable D4.5 presents the initial development and validation of an autonomous drill planning and execution system designed for operation in deep and abandoned mining environments. The work addresses the core objectives of Task 4.5 by defining a complete mission workflow, integrating perception and motion planning capabilities, and implementing a communication framework to support coordinated operation within a modular robotic system.

The system architecture brings together onboard sensing, surface analysis, and robotic manipulation in a unified perceive-and-act framework capable of identifying optimal drilling locations and generating motion plans for precise execution. These components have been implemented and validated within a Gazebo-based simulation environment that realistically emulates mine tunnel conditions, supporting safe, scalable, and repeatable testing of mission logic under representative constraints.

In addition, a communication layer has been developed to enable inter-robot coordination, supporting the envisioned distributed mission execution and laying the groundwork for a fully autonomous, collaborative fleet. The progress made in simulation demonstrates the feasibility of the proposed approach and sets the stage for upcoming work focused on drill execution, Stinger Robot control, and real-world system integration.

Currently, the project has reached TRL 3. This has been accomplished through the development of key sub-components, including communication protocols, manipulator mapping, drill plan adjustment algorithms, and mine surface analysis tools. Each of these components has undergone separate testing in both simulated environments and laboratory settings. The upcoming Task 5.5 will focus on integrating these technologies into a unified framework to perform autonomous drilling within a lab environment, aiming to achieve TRL 4 or 5.

Overall, the outcomes presented in this deliverable fulfill the objectives of Task 4.5 and establish a solid foundation for the continued development and deployment of autonomous drilling capabilities within the broader scope of the PERSEPHONE project.

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7 References

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